
EGI Federation Annual Report 2025

Driving European Research with
Advanced Digital Solutions

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Foreword

Volker Guelzow
EGI Council Chair

2025 marks the start of my second term as EGI Council Chair. Among the most significant achievements of the past year has been the definition and adoption of the EGI Federation Strategy 2026–2030. Developed through extensive consultation across our community, the strategy establishes a shared vision for the Federation's future at a time when Europe's research and innovation landscape is undergoing profound transformation.

The strategy positions EGI as a key contributor to Europe's evolving digital research ecosystem by expanding access to advanced computing, data and AI capabilities, by promoting a more integrated and interoperable European infrastructure landscape,

and by strengthening the Federation's role as an innovation ecosystem that brings together research communities, Research Infrastructures, technology providers and scientific institutions.

Beyond its strategic objectives, the new strategy represents an important collective commitment. It reflects the willingness of our members and partners to work together towards a common vision, recognising that the challenges facing science today can only be addressed through cooperation, openness and shared investment in capabilities that benefit the wider research community.

The adoption of this strategy provides a strong foundation for the years ahead and reaffirms EGI's role as a trusted partner in enabling scientific excellence, fostering innovation, and supporting a connected and collaborative European Research Area.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the members of the EGI Council for their dedication, insight and commitment throughout this process. The strategy is the result of constructive dialogue, mutual trust and a shared sense of responsibility towards

the future of the Federation. The Council members, representing the diversity and strength of our community, have demonstrated once again that consensus-building and collaboration remain among EGI's greatest assets. Their contributions have been instrumental in shaping a strategy that is both ambitious and firmly grounded in the needs of our members, users and partners.

At a time when fragmentation and short-term interests can too easily prevail, the collective effort invested in defining this common direction serves as a powerful reminder of what can be achieved when organisations come together around shared values and a common purpose. I am grateful for the trust placed in the Council and confident that, together, we will continue to strengthen the Federation and its contribution to European and global research.

Tiziana Ferrari
Director of the EGI Foundation

As we reflect on the past year, we do so against a backdrop of profound global challenges. Ongoing conflicts, geopolitical tensions, and growing tendencies towards fragmentation, isolation, and individualism continue to test the values of openness, cooperation, and trust upon which scientific progress depends.

In this context, one of my foremost priorities has been to support the growth of the EGI Federation by strengthening its role as a catalyst for collaboration. Research and innovation communities have a unique opportunity and responsibility to demonstrate the power of working together towards shared goals.

Over the past year, we have reinforced our collaboration

with international digital infrastructures, advancing a vision of an interconnected ecosystem of complementary and aligned initiatives. By fostering coordination rather than duplication, and partnership rather than competition, we contribute to a stronger and more resilient global research landscape.

Equally important has been the deepening of our collaboration with Research Infrastructures and research-performing organisations across Europe. This collective effort has culminated in the establishment of a joint research programme that brings together more than twenty Research Infrastructures and supports tens of collaborative research projects. Such achievements are a testament to what can be accomplished when diverse communities unite around common scientific ambitions.

I firmly believe that EGI and the Research Infrastructure community can serve as an example of how cooperation transcends institutional, disciplinary, and national boundaries. Together, we demonstrate that unity, mutual trust, and coordinated action remain powerful drivers of progress. In a

world increasingly shaped by uncertainty and division, our shared commitment to advancing research for the benefit of society represents a common good that connects us all.

The successes highlighted in this report are the result of the dedication, expertise, and collaborative spirit of our members, partners, and stakeholders. I would like to express my sincere gratitude to all those who have contributed to this journey. Their commitment continues to strengthen our community and reinforces the importance of working together to enable excellence in research and innovation.

As we look ahead, we will continue to build bridges across communities, infrastructures, and borders, ensuring that collaboration remains at the heart of our mission and that science continues to serve as a force for openness, knowledge, and shared progress.

Introduction

2025 marks a defining year in the continued evolution of the EGI Federation as a cornerstone of Europe's research and innovation landscape. Over the past year, EGI has further strengthened its role as Europe's largest federated digital research infrastructure into a Research Data & Compute Continuum, conducting R&D that sits between thematic research communities and national/institutional research HTC/HPC/Cloud.

Enabling data-intensive science across disciplines and borders, while deepening its alignment with European strategic priorities in Open Science, Artificial Intelligence, and data-driven research.

The federation continues to demonstrate a strong balance between operational excellence and strategic development. The expansion of services across compute, data, identity, and AI capabilities reflects both technical maturity and a clear commitment to supporting the evolving needs of Research Infrastructures and scientific

communities. The growing adoption of EGI services by ESFRI Research Infrastructures and international collaborations highlights increasing trust in the federation's long-term sustainability and impact.

Beyond technological progress, the strength of the EGI Federation lies in its community. The continued commitment of partners, service providers, and user communities underpins its success. Expanding engagement, reflected in increased service uptake, training activities, and collaborative projects, demonstrates the value of a

federated model based on shared responsibility and co-development.

Looking ahead, EGI is well positioned to play an even more central role in Europe's digital research ecosystem. The transition toward integrated compute-data-AI continuums, the evolution of Trusted Research Environments, and continued alignment with European policy frameworks such as the European Research Area and the Digital Decade will further reinforce its strategic relevance.

About EGI_

Advanced Computing Services for a Data-Driven Future

The EGI Foundation operates and coordinates the EGI Federation, a pan-European digital infrastructure that enables data-intensive research through federated computing, data, and identity services. Building on more than two decades of continuous service delivery, EGI connects over 200 service providers across Europe and beyond, enabling researchers to access scalable computing and data resources through a trusted and interoperable ecosystem.

Beyond its role as a federation operator, EGI is evolving into a strategic research and innovation player for European research. Through its value streams model, EGI not only delivers operational services but also co-designs and develops advanced digital capabilities in collaboration with research communities, service providers, and technology partners. This includes domain-specific platforms, AI-enabled services, and integrated compute-data solutions that extend from infrastructure provision to applied research environments.

The value streams represent EGI's core areas of activity, structuring how the federation delivers services, supports scientific computing, and drives innovation:

- **Power the federation:** enabling trusted federation coordination through platforms, policies, and governance
- **Enable scientific computing:** providing seamless access to services and value-added capabilities within an AI-ready compute-data continuum
- **Conducting research:** with a European network of R&D organisations in computer science applied to data-intensive scientific cases

Vision

A future where advanced computing and shared data resources seamlessly empower every field of research to achieve transformative discoveries and address global challenges.

Mission

We accelerate the frontier of data-intensive research by federating digital capabilities, fostering collaboration, and driving continuous innovation.

Ambition 2030

Europe's essential federated AI-ready compute-data continuum for research communities, where innovation and investment compound for pan-European impact Power the Federation Value Streams Enable Scientific Computing Enable Sustained Innovation.

Key Highlights

- January**
 - Signing the first of 11 Service Level Agreements (SLAs) concluded in 2025, starting with Euro-Argo ERIC.
- February**
 - 15th anniversary celebrated.
- March**
 - Flagship project RI-SCALE for AI-driven data exploitation platforms kicks-off.
 - SAGE project kicks off in support of the Green Deal Data Space, with EGI participating as a key technology provider.
- April**
 - Flagship project EOSC Data Commons launched with a focus on research data discovery, reuse, and interoperability.
- May**
 - EGI Federation accounts the largest peak in use of monthly computing resources since ever!
- June**
 - EGI2025 Conference in Santander with 350+ participants.
 - European e-Infrastructures Assembly defines EOSC Node support model and strengthens EOSC EU Node rollout.
- July**
 - Coordination between EGI, EUDAT, GÉANT, OpenAIRE, PRACE strengthened with alignment on EOSC strategy, governance, and joint outreachour roadmap for the future.
- August**
 - 2 EGI Flagship projects iImagine and interTwin successfully concluded
 - interTwin delivered the Digital Twin Engine.
 - iImagine delivered the AI Platform for aquatic science.
- September**
 - Signing one of five Memoranda of Understanding concluded in the year, including a renewed international agreement with Computer Network Information Center, China.
- October**
 - ENVRI-Hub NEXT celebrates 18-month milestone with the development of the environmental research platform.
- November**
 - Council adopts the EGI Federation Strategy 2026–2029, outlining the Federation's future direction and advancing the data and compute continuum vision.
 - Co-Authoring the Crete Declaration, Uniting European Science for One Health.
- December**
 - SCIANCE project kicks off to coordinate AI in science across Europe, with EGI leading the communication and engagement, and infrastructure roadmap development.
 - EGI Foundation staff meeting in Amsterdam.

Key Numbers

In 2025, EGI expanded its global reach while strengthening strategic engagement with research infrastructures and advancing its role as an innovation and solution provider.

163K

Researchers supported

200+

Active research communities

210+

Federated service providers

190+

Countries with active users

42

Countries in the EGI infrastructure

~2.6K /year

Scientific publications supported*

20+

Research infrastructures collaborating in R&D

* supported via EGI-enabled workflows (OpenAIRE-based attribution)

Empowering Research

New

R&D collaborations with INSTRUCT-ERIC¹, EPOS-ERIC², Euro-BioImaging ERIC³, and Km3NeT⁴

40+

Research Infrastructures engaged across operations, projects, and research & development collaborations

19

New scientific communities partnered with EGI to support research & innovation

Innovation & Solution Delivery

4

New services being developed in R&I projects

1

New service prototyped in 2025

9

Platforms co-developed with Research Infrastructures

2

AI-enabled research environments deployed

¹INSTRUCT-ERIC: European research infrastructure for structural biology
²EPOS-ERIC: European Plate Observing System
³Euro-BioImaging ERIC: The gateway to European biological and biomedical imaging
⁴Km3NeT: The Cubic Kilometre Neutrino Telescope

Our Users

The breadth of the EGI Federation's impact is best understood through the diversity and scale of its user base. In 2025, continued growth in adoption reflects not only increasing demand for federated digital infrastructure, but also the trust placed in EGI by research communities worldwide.

From large-scale Research Infrastructures to individual research teams, EGI supports a dynamic and interconnected ecosystem of users working across disciplines, sectors, and geographic boundaries. This community spans established scientific domains as well as emerging fields.

Strategic Partnerships with Research Infrastructures

40+

Research Infrastructures engaged across operations, projects, and R&D collaborations

5

Memoranda of Understanding with Research Infrastructures

11

Service Level Agreements with Research Infrastructures

41

Research Infrastructures involved in R&D collaborations

R&D partnerships with European Research Infrastructures

WATCH THE SERIES: EGI COMMUNITY VOICES

Research Impact in Action: In 2025, EGI published a series of community videos showcasing how researchers, projects and infrastructure providers use EGI services in real scientific workflows across disciplines.

FROM SCALE TO IMPACT

In 2025, EGI's expanding research programme and its ecosystem of research performing organisations from its members, and innovators and experts from Research Infrastructures of pan-European relevance and user communities, are the expression of a deep integration in the research ecosystem.

By connecting research teams and infrastructure providers from multiple scientific domains, research institutes and countries, the EGI partners' ecosystem is ideally placed to be a key enabler of digital transformation in science.

translates into concrete scientific outcomes and service innovation.

The following sections highlight how this scale

Activities and Impact

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01

Empowering Research

Building on the best practices and methodologies established in previous years, EGI's 2025 engagement strategy focused on forging new partnerships with research collaborations and ESFRI Research Infrastructures with advanced digital requirements. The objective was to join forces in co-design and collaborative computer science research, advancing the state of the art of digital solutions while addressing emerging scientific challenges.

01 Empowering Research

Community Engagement: Key Figures and Strategic Shift

In 2025, EGI initiated collaborations with 19 new scientific communities and 4 Research Infrastructures, reflecting a shift from a predominantly quantitative expansion approach toward a more strategic, quality-driven engagement model.

The growing portfolio of research activities and strategic collaborations further consolidates EGI's network of research laboratories and institutions as a significant contributor to Europe's research and innovation landscape. By bringing together expertise from computer science, digital infrastructures, and diverse scientific domains, this network strengthens multidisciplinary research support and fosters innovation across disciplinary boundaries. Through its partnerships with research communities and Research Infrastructures, EGI contributes to advancing excellent science and amplifying its societal impact, enabling discoveries and solutions that address some of the most pressing challenges facing Europe and the world.

At the same time, by strengthening research and development capacity across its Federation and partner communities, EGI contributes to the creation of new digital technologies, services, and methodologies that support Europe's digital transformation. These efforts help reinforce European technological capabilities and strategic autonomy, ensuring that critical digital solutions are developed, governed, and sustained within an open, collaborative, and research-driven European ecosystem.

Highlights

163K

Total users in 2025 (+41% annual growth)

New

R&D collaborations with INSTRUCT-ERIC¹, EPOS-ERIC², Euro-BiImaging ERIC³, and Km3NeT⁴

40+

Research Infrastructures engaged across operations, projects, and research & development collaborations

19

New scientific communities partnered with EGI to support research & innovation

~2,6K

Scientific publications supported annually⁵

¹INSTRUCT-ERIC: European research infrastructure for structural biology

²EPOS-ERIC: European Plate Observing System

³Euro-BiImaging ERIC: The gateway to European biological and biomedical imaging

⁴Km3NeT: The Cubic Kilometre Neutrino Telescope

⁵Based on OpenAIRE statistics

EGI User Successes Across Disciplines

These stories underline the impact of the EGI's infrastructure in advancing research across diverse disciplines. From accelerating data-intensive analyses to supporting innovative methodologies, the federation's infrastructure empowers researchers to tackle pressing scientific and societal challenges with greater efficiency, reproducibility, and impact.

PHYSICAL SCIENCES AND ENGINEERING

Supporting the JUNO Neutrino Experiment with Global Computing

JUNO¹⁰ is a flagship international neutrino physics project located in Guangdong Province, China. Designed as one of the most precise neutrino detectors ever constructed, JUNO brings together a broad global collaboration of research institutes and universities. Its primary scientific goal is to determine the neutrino mass hierarchy, a fundamental open question in particle physics. In addition, JUNO aims to measure neutrino oscillation parameters with unprecedented precision and to conduct detailed studies of solar, atmospheric, geoneutrinos, and neutrinos from potential supernova events.

To achieve these ambitious objectives, JUNO relies on large-scale simulation, data processing, storage, and distributed analysis capabilities

offered by the EGI resource providers. The EGI Internal Portfolio services play a crucial role in delivering and continuously evolving the computing and data infrastructure required by the experiment.

Did you know?

The technologies and data analysis methods developed for experiments like JUNO often find applications beyond physics, including in medical imaging, radiation detection, and large-scale data processing used in many industries.

EGI contributing institutions: Institute of High Energy Physics of the Chinese Academy of Science, CNRS, INFN, JINR, and JISC

EARTH SCIENCES

Next-generation hub for Earth Observation data

The EGI Federation supports the NextGEOSS¹¹ initiative by providing a federated, scalable infrastructure for accessing and analysing Earth Observation (EO) data. This environment enables seamless integration of distributed datasets and services.

EGI resources provided by CESNET¹², combined with secure access via EGI Check-in (GRNET), ensure reliable performance for large-scale data processing and analytics.

Did you know?

Earth Observation data supports climate monitoring, disaster response, agriculture, and urban planning, helping societies make informed decisions about our planet.

EGI contributing institutions: CESNET · GRNET

¹⁰Jiangmen Underground Neutrino Observatory, <https://juno.ihep.cas.cn>

¹¹NextGEOSS is a centralised European Earth observation data hub and platform, <https://nextgeoss.eu/>

¹²CESNET: Czech Education and Scientific Network, <https://www.cesnet.cz/en>

ENVIRONMENT

Enabling global coastal observation and forecasting

CoastPredict, endorsed by the UN Ocean Decade, improves how coastal systems are monitored and forecast by combining real-time data with predictive modelling.

EGI supports this effort by enabling the GlobalCoast cloud platform, built on scalable computing (Dask) and object storage. In 2025, infrastructure from TUBITAK ULAKBIM powered large-scale coastal data processing, with secure access via EGI Check-in.

This environment supports research, operational forecasting, and evidence-based coastal management.

Did you know?

Better coastal forecasting helps protect communities from storms, flooding, and climate change impacts, improving safety and economic resilience worldwide.

EGI contributing institutions: TUBITAK ULAKBIM · GRNET

BIODIVERSITY CONSERVATION

Making biodiversity data accessible and actionable

OpenBioMaps is an open-source platform that enables researchers, conservationists, and citizen scientists to collect, manage, and analyse biodiversity data.

In 2025, around 1,000 users relied on EGI-supported infrastructure to run data-intensive analyses, reflecting growing demand for accessible biodiversity tools.

Did you know?

Accessible biodiversity data helps track species decline, protect ecosystems, and guide conservation policies that directly impact food systems and environmental health.

EGI contributing institutions: HUN-REN SZTAKI

NATURAL SCIENCES

Advancing bioinformatics services

NBIS¹³ provides bioinformatics and data science support to the Swedish life science community.

In 2025, 7,3K+ users accessed NBIS platforms powered by EGI resources. Increased reliability and growing demand, especially in protein structure prediction, have driven steady usage growth.

Did you know?

Tools for protein analysis are essential for understanding diseases and developing new treatments, including vaccines and targeted therapies.

EGI contributing institutions: INFN, CNRS, TUBITAK ULAKBIM

PLANETARY SCIENCES

Cloud infrastructure for planetary data analysis

The Europlanet-GMAP project supports planetary scientists with cloud-based tools for analysing and mapping planetary data.

EGI partner INFN provides computing resources (48 vCPU, 256 GB RAM, 20 TB storage) to power Jupyter-based analysis environments.

Studying planetary surfaces helps us understand Earth's evolution, climate processes, and potential future environmental changes.

EGI contributing institutions: INFN

Did you know?

¹³NBIS: National Bioinformatics Infrastructure Sweden, <https://www.nbis.se/>

SOCIAL SCIENCES

Studying youth engagement in democracy

The YouReACT¹⁴ project explores why socially active young people in rural regions often do not engage politically.

EGI supports secure cross-border data sharing between Germany and Austria, ensuring GDPR compliance. The University of Innsbruck uses EGI DataHub (500 GB storage) with secure access via Check-in.

Did you know?

Understanding youth engagement helps strengthen democratic participation and supports more inclusive policymaking.

EGI contributing institutions: CYFRONET · GRNET

CULTURAL HERITAGE

Extending cultural heritage with XR

EUreka3D-XR¹⁵ brings extended reality (XR) tools to cultural heritage, enabling immersive experiences such as virtual reconstructions and interactive storytelling.

The infrastructure is powered by Kubernetes-based cloud resources (120 vCPU, 1 TB RAM, 20 TB storage), supporting XR tool deployment and data access via EGI services.

3D models are stored in the EUreka3D Data Hub, supported by EGI DataHub, ensuring secure and scalable access for cultural institutions.

Did you know?

Digital heritage tools make culture more accessible, allowing people to explore historical sites, artefacts, and stories from anywhere in the world.

EGI contributing institutions: GRNET, WCSS, CYFRONET

¹⁴YouReACT: Young People in Remote Regions – Prospects for Strengthening Democratic Attitudes and Participation, <https://www.uibk.ac.at/de/geschichte-ekw/institut/ekw/forschung/youreact/>
¹⁵EUreka3D-XR: European Union's REKconstructed content in 3D to produce XR experiences, <https://eureka3d.eu/>

PROJECT HIGHLIGHT

ENVRI-HUB Next, now in its second year, is a project that aims to consolidate discovery, access, and knowledge across 10 RIs in the ENVRI¹⁶ community.

During 2025, significant landmarks were achieved with the deployment of the ENVRI-Hub – an integrated system offering a suite of services for cross-RI, cross-domain, and cross-border access.

The ENVRI-Hub has achieved unprecedented integration across diverse environmental domains, enabling both scientific researchers and machine-to-machine (M2M) systems to seamlessly exploit distributed in situ observational datasets, federated services, and specialised knowledge bases. By establishing a robust data and service interoperability backbone, the Hub provides the machine-actionable foundation necessary for emerging AI-driven analytics, ultimately accelerating breakthrough discoveries in Earth system science and reinforcing EU climate policy execution.

LLMs¹⁸. These services make ECVs comparable across RIs and accessible through Virtual Research Environments, such as Jupyter Notebooks deployed by CESNET.

Leveraging the technical capabilities of Check-in, EGI provides ENVRI-ID to support single sign-on to ENVRI data and services accessible through the ENVRI-Hub¹⁹. ENVRI ID connects directly with each RI's AAI (Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure), enriching existing solutions for cross-infrastructure access.

In its final phase, the project will focus on bringing the ENVRI-Hub into full production, establishing operational best practices, and scaling up both ECV encoding and user adoption.

Did you know?

Interoperable environmental data systems like ENVRI-Hub help scientists combine observations from different domains to better understand the Earth system, climate change and ecosystem dynamics.

EGI contributing institutions: LIP · CESNET · GRNET

EGI supported the Hub by hosting it on its infrastructure through federation providers LIP¹⁷ and CESNET. Cloud provision and industry-standard DevOps practices ensure that all applications are cloud-compatible and deployed via pipelines that enforce security checks, code standards, and smooth transitions from staging to production.

The project follows a biannual release cycle, delivering a mature suite of services that equips scientists with the tools and knowledge needed for cross-disciplinary environmental research. The interoperability layer aligns Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) across services using standardised ontologies, catalogs, data access libraries, and knowledge-based support through

¹⁶Environmental Research Infrastructure community, www.envri.eu
¹⁷LIP: Laboratory of Instrumentation and Experimental Particle Physics, <https://www.lip.pt/>
¹⁸LLM: Large Language Model
¹⁹Single Sign-On

02

Accelerating Research and Innovation

02 Accelerating Research and Innovation

Technical Innovation and New Services

Thanks to its strong research and development programme, EGI was well positioned in 2025 to bridge cutting-edge research and digital transformation. Throughout the year, the Federation continued to evolve its service portfolio to support a more integrated, secure, and seamless digital environment for research, spanning cloud, HPC,

data, identity, and AI services. Particular emphasis was placed on developing a unified compute and data continuum, strengthening interoperability across European infrastructures, and improving accessibility and usability for research communities, thereby enabling more efficient and collaborative scientific workflows.

COMPUTE

Federation Across Cloud, HPC, and HTC

An integrated and interoperable computing environment that enables users and applications to seamlessly access and combine computing resources across different platforms, locations, and technologies—from edge devices and cloud services to high-throughput and high-performance computing systems—according to their specific requirements.

EGI advanced its contribution to a federated compute continuum, integrating cloud, high-throughput, and HPC resources under a unified access and identity layer. This strengthens the ability of research communities to run complex, distributed workloads across infrastructures seamlessly. Characteristics of the EGI approach are integration of hundreds of heterogeneous resources, workload portability, data proximity and interoperability.

A key development was the continued maturation of container-based and orchestration capabilities, improving portability, reproducibility, and operational consistency across providers.

Strategic takeaway:

EGI is evolving into a coherent compute continuum for European research, enabling seamless execution of workloads across cloud, HPC, and HTC environments.

Technical snapshot

- Production deployment of the EGI Artefact Registry for container images
- Expanded image synchronisation across FedCloud providers
- Kubernetes federation via Cloud Container Compute
- Dynamic DNS integration with Infrastructure Manager
- Enhanced Notebooks and Replay services with Check-in tokens
- Early HPC integration via Kubernetes-to-supercomputer workflows

WATCH THE VIDEO:
SOLVING THE RESEARCH COMPUTE CRUNCH

Modern science is generating more data than ever. EGI provides the scalable computing and data infrastructure needed to turn this data into discovery.

[HTTPS://GO.EGI.EU/HKLQZ](https://go.egi.eu/hklqz)

DATA SERVICES

Strengthening the Compute-Data Continuum

A data continuum is an integrated and interoperable environment that enables distributed data to flow seamlessly across the entire data lifecycle from generation and acquisition to storage, processing, sharing, preservation, and reuse while maintaining accessibility, quality, security, and compliance with agreed standards and policies.

In 2025, EGI strengthened the integration between data and compute services, enabling more efficient and interoperable data-driven research workflows. This supports the principle of bringing computation closer to data across federated infrastructures.

The federation also advanced FAIR data support and interoperability across domains, improving how data is discovered, accessed, and processed.

Strategic takeaway:

EGI is enabling a compute-data continuum where data access and processing are seamlessly integrated across infrastructures.

Technical snapshot

- Object Storage service definition (production target 2026)
- Check-in integration with data orchestration and transfer services
- HPC data staging interoperability improvements
- Trusted Research Environment (TRE) landscape analysis
- DataHub S3 TRL8 maturity and metadata support (DataCite, OpenAIRE)
- Transition from Online Storage to Object Storage architecture
- Data Transfer API enhancements and HPC pilots

Identity, Trust and Security

In 2025, EGI consolidated its Identity and Access Management capabilities, extending secure and scalable access capabilities across federated compute and data services. The evolution of Check-in enables both human and machine identities to operate securely in distributed environments.

Work also progressed toward next-generation IAM models, enabling more dynamic and policy-driven access aligned with emerging European infrastructure needs.

Strategic takeaway:

EGI IAM is evolving into a policy-driven trust and access layer for European research infrastructures, supporting both human and machine identities.

Technical snapshot

- Federated Proxy scalability improvements
- Keycloak-based Advanced Group Management
- Expansion of OIDC token-based access
- Policy-based access aligned with AARC guidelines
- Early SSI and verifiable credentials exploration
- EGI Secrets Store production maturity
- Integration with EOSC Beyond and Community AAI deployments

AI services

In 2025, EGI expanded federated AI capabilities, including LLM services and AI-enabled workflows integrated into research environments. These services bring AI closer to data and compute within federated infrastructures.

This marks a key step toward AI-native research environments in Europe, where AI becomes a core infrastructure capability rather than an external tool.

Strategic takeaway:

EGI is laying the foundations for AI-native research infrastructure, embedding AI capabilities directly into federated compute and data environments.

Technical snapshot

- Federated LLM service with OpenAI-compatible API
- Secure conversational AI access for research users
- Federated inference across providers
- Check-in integration for AI access control
- RAG and workflow integration support
- EOSC Data Commons Matchmaker & Data Player
- RI-SCALE Data Exploitation Platform design

PROJECT HIGHLIGHT

Supporting the Establishment of EOSC as a Trusted European Research Commons

Primary domain of research: Data Management and Data Engineering

Started in Q2 2025, EOSC Data Commons contributes to establishing EOSC as the European Research Commons – an open, trusted, and federated ecosystem enabling seamless access to high-quality interoperable research outputs and services. The project brings together a pan-European consortium of open source technology providers, national and thematic data repositories, and user communities, which actively contribute through co-design, testing, and validation activities based on real scientific use cases. By engaging 12 national and institutional data repositories, the project aims to support the integration of EOSC Nodes in the emerging EOSC Federation.

In 2025, the project delivered a first proof-of-concept release of two core services:

- EOSC Matchmaker
- EOSC Data Player

Together, these services support researchers across the full data lifecycle, improving FAIR data practices, data discovery, analysis, and reproducibility of scientific workflows.

EOSC Matchmaker introduces AI-assisted discovery, enabling natural language queries across federated repositories and linking datasets with relevant tools and applications across providers. EOSC Data Player enables execution of tools directly on distributed datasets, simplifying access to the compute continuum in a fully interoperable way.

PROJECT HIGHLIGHT

Data Exploitation Platforms

Primary domain of research: Distributed Data Systems

The RI-SCALE project, coordinated by EGI Foundation and started in 2025, is developing Data Exploitation Platforms (DEPs) to enable research infrastructures to transform large-scale data assets into actionable knowledge. The DEP is designed as a scalable platform enabling seamless integration of data, compute, and AI services across cloud and HPC environments. It supports efficient data movement, advanced analytics, and AI-driven processing workflows.

In 2025, the project focused on the design and architecture of the DEP, covering:

- Data management and lifecycle design
- AI frameworks and machine learning infrastructure
- AAI integration
- Credit and resource management models

A comprehensive validation plan was also defined, covering eight scientific use cases and four technical use cases, ensuring the platform is grounded in real-world requirements. The first DEP release (planned for Q1 2026) will deliver the core building blocks of this vision, including:

- Data Life Cycle Management with policy-driven data movement and integration with compute sites
- AI Life Cycle Management, including an AI Model Hub, distributed machine learning frameworks, provenance tracking, and early AI agent support for training and inference workflows
- Policy-based access control mechanisms ensuring enforceable data access rules and embargo management in a standards-based way
- Resource and credit management foundations for CPU, GPU, and storage accounting with sustainability-aware tracking.

03

Fostering Collaboration

03 Fostering Collaboration

Empowering Research Infrastructures

Close cooperation with ESFRI Research Infrastructures is a key element of EGI's role in strengthening Europe's research and innovation ecosystem. Through federated compute, data, and identity capabilities, EGI supports RIs in scaling operations, improving interoperability, and delivering advanced digital environments to their communities.

This section presents selected examples of EGI's operational collaborations with ESFRI RIs.

EPOS-ERIC

Federated computing for solid Earth science

EPOS is a European Research Infrastructure that integrates data, services, and facilities for solid Earth science, enabling researchers to study earthquakes, volcanoes, and tectonic processes across distributed datasets.

EGI and EPOS joined forces to work in co-design, development, testing and piloting of suitable solutions for the implementation of a EPOS distributed compute platform for data integration and analysis across multiple institutions. These capabilities enable scalable processing of heterogeneous Earth science data and improve interoperability across national research centres.

Key contributors: SRCE · GRNET

EURO-ARGO ERIC

Cloud infrastructure for global ocean observation

EURO-ARGO²⁰ coordinates Europe's contribution to the global Argo programme, using autonomous floats to collect continuous measurements of the world's oceans.

EGI enables the deployment of the ARGO Global Data Assembly Centre (GDAC), providing scalable cloud infrastructure for ingestion, processing, quality control, archiving, and near real-time distribution of oceanographic data.

Key contributors: CNRS · GRNET

EURO-BIOIMAGING ERIC

Distributed imaging training and analysis environments

Euro-BioImaging is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium operating a distributed network of imaging facilities that provide open access to advanced biological and biomedical imaging technologies, along with services for image data generation, analysis, and FAIR archiving.

EGI collaborates with Euro-Bioimaging to test and adapt software solutions federated cloud infrastructure that enables Euro-BioImaging to run distributed training and remote analysis environments through the BAND (BioImage ANalysis Desktop) platform. This allows users to access advanced image analysis tools in a unified environment without local installation, improving accessibility to complex imaging workflows and enabling scalable training across multiple sites.

In 2025, BAND was used in 10 training events involving 200+ trainees, including PhD students, imaging scientists, and facility staff from across Europe and beyond. This demonstrates how federated cloud-based environments can directly support distributed scientific training and knowledge transfer across a large user community.

EGI also collaborates with Euro-BioImaging in the context of the RI-SCALE project, where it is one of the leading Research Infrastructures co-developing DEPs.

Key contributors: CESNET

²⁰Euro-Argo: European Research Infrastructure Consortium for Ocean Observation, <https://www.euro-argo.eu/>

Cloud services for structural biology workflows

INSTRUCT-ERIC supports structural biology research by providing access to advanced experimental facilities and digital services such as ARIA (access and workflow management) and CRIMS (crystallography data management).

EGL advances software capabilities of a Kubernetes-based cloud infrastructure that enables scalable deployment, orchestration, and secure operation of these services, ensuring they can support growing user demand across the research community.

Key contributors: CNRS · GRNET

Federated computing for neutrino astronomy

KM3NeT²¹ is a large-scale distributed Research Infrastructure that operates a deep-sea neutrino telescope designed to detect high-energy neutrinos from cosmic sources, requiring intensive simulation, reconstruction, and data analysis workflows.

With KM3NeT EGL intends to advance technical solutions that implement federated layer that supports KM3NeT's large-scale computational needs, adapting by existing solutions to the specific needs of KM3NeT and enabling distributed processing of simulation and analysis workloads across the EGL Federation. This ensures that data-intensive workflows can be executed efficiently across multiple sites, supporting the production of high-precision scientific results in neutrino astronomy.

Key contributors: CNRS, NIFHEF, SURF

Strategic Research Infrastructure Partnerships (MoUs)

In 2025, EGL strengthened long-term collaboration with major Research Infrastructures through Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs), formalising cooperation on federated computing, data services, and identity integration.

These agreements establish structured collaboration with:

- **KM3NeT:** deep-sea neutrino telescope infrastructure for high-energy astrophysics
- **JUNO:** international neutrino physics experiment based in China
- **EPOS-ERIC:** European solid Earth science Research Infrastructure

- **PITHIA-NRF:** Plasmasphere Ionosphere Thermosphere Integrated Research Environment and Access Services: a Network of Research Facilities
- **Computer Network Information Center:** (CNIC, China) – renewed MoU supporting continued collaboration on distributed research infrastructure and data services

Through these partnerships, EGL supports the integration of scalable computing and data services into large-scale scientific infrastructures, ensuring long-term sustainability and interoperability of distributed research environments.

Lilli Freda, Executive Director of EPOS ERIC.

The EGL Federation brings outstanding technical expertise and computing capacity that are vital to our vision of integrated, accessible solid Earth science data.

Yin Chen, Senior Community Support Officer at EGL Foundation

By signing the PITHIA-NRF MoU, 17 organisations commit to a shared governance framework that sustains collaboration beyond the project lifetime, supports strategic decision-making, and ensures the continued operation of the e-Science Centre as a core community service.

²¹KM3NeT: Cubic Kilometre Neutrino Telescope, <https://www.km3net.org/>

International Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

EGL's international collaboration and outreach activities ensure that the federation remains a connected, interoperable, and sustainable research ecosystem. These activities complement operational service delivery by expanding adoption, strengthening interoperability with partner infrastructures, and supporting long-term community engagement across disciplines and regions.

Rather than isolated events or initiatives, EGL's engagement model integrates structured mechanisms for ecosystem growth, including recurring community programmes, cross-infrastructure collaborations, and coordinated participation in European and international research frameworks.

Key mechanisms include:

- **Scaling EGL's global research ecosystem:** EGL established the EGL International Liaison Group (ILG) as a mechanism to further enhance collaboration with key digital research infrastructures worldwide. Recognising that effective support for modern science relies on the combined capabilities of multiple leading infrastructures, the ILG aims to foster closer cooperation, alignment, and exchange across international partners and peer e-infrastructure beyond Europe. With EGL infrastructure currently spanning data centres across 42 countries, this framework provides a structured approach to engaging with a globally distributed ecosystem of research infrastructures

and supporting research communities with international reach. The ILG is organised around seven geographical areas and will begin its outreach activities in 2026, contributing to a more connected, inclusive, and interoperable global digital environment for research reflecting the inherently borderless nature of science.

- **Community engagement activities:** EGL uses a range of community engagement activities to build, support, and grow its user and stakeholder community, especially user communities, service providers, EGL national members (the NGIs), technology partners, and European e-infrastructure collaborators. These activities aim to foster collaboration, share knowledge, and make EGL's services more widely known and used.
- **Annual conferences:** EGL's annual conference brings together researchers, infrastructure providers, policymakers, and technology partners to share results, discuss developments, and strengthen collaboration across the ecosystem.
- **Trainings and webinars:** EGL delivers regular training sessions and webinars covering service usage, best practices in data and compute infrastructures, and technical skill development, supporting both new and advanced users.
- **Community Managers Group:** A network of community experts that supports sustainable engagement, coordination, and growth of research communities using EGL services.
- **Engagement through EC-funded projects:** EGL collaborates with Research Infrastructures and scientific

communities through European projects. Besides collecting requirements and co-developing new services across the federated infrastructure, EGL also contributes to coordination activities or policy development actions.

- **Collaboration with European e-infrastructure:** through the e-Infrastructure Assembly EGL works closely with organisations such as GÉANT, EUDAT, OpenAIRE, and PRACE to ensure interoperability, align strategies, engage research communities and strengthen cross-community service delivery.
- **EGL Access Calls:** The EGL Access Call provides structured access to federated cloud, high-throughput computing, storage, and data services for Research Infrastructures, scientific communities, and innovation projects.
- **Documentation and onboarding:** EGL provides tailored documentation and onboarding materials to support both users and service providers in advancing, adopting and integrating EGL services.

Community engagement in numbers (2025)

- EGL2025, the EGL flagship conference with **350+** participants, **20** partners, **136** contributions, **25+** sessions, meetings and workshops
- **33** research projects
- **42** applications received through the EGL Access Calls
- **11** Community Managers meetings organised

Developing Skills and Competencies

EGI supports researchers and service providers through continuous learning and skills development, combining hands-on training, community knowledge exchange, and the application of established operational best practices such as FitSM, the lightweight²² IT service management standard. This approach strengthens both individual expertise and organisational maturity across the federation, contributing to the reliable operation and evolution of distributed computing and data services.

By promoting shared learning and practical engagement with EGI services, the federation enables users to effectively operate in data-intensive and distributed environments, improving the uptake, usability, and sustainability of shared research infrastructure.

Training to utilise the services

EGI delivers a structured training programme to support the adoption and effective use of its services. The EGI Webinar Programme provides regular, accessible online training sessions for research communities across Europe and beyond. These are complemented by hands-on training activities delivered during EGI Conferences, international workshops, and community events, where participants can gain practical experience directly with EGI services, supported by experts from the federation.

In 2025, EGI and its members organised 11 webinars and 4 training sessions/workshops, engaging a broad international audience and reinforcing community adoption of federated services.

Highlights

11

webinars through the EGI Webinar Programme

270

webinar participants from 19 countries reached

580+

Views on YouTube

4

Training sessions with 230+ live trainees

²²<https://www.egi.eu/service/fit-sm-training/>

Training Testimonials

//

Natacha Vitrat @Genopole

D4Gen hackathon provided an unique environment to think globally and "outside the box". This event highlighted the importance of multidisciplinary to implement innovative approaches and solve bottlenecks. The score of satisfaction with EGI infrastructure was 4.4 out of 5. Congratulations!

//

Darren Thompson @University of Exeter, co-organiser, with Caron Jacobs, of an image analysis course at Cape Town University

I've used the BAND platform for several training courses until now, and each time it's been a great experience. Having instant access to GPU-equipped virtual machines is invaluable when working with modern deep learning segmentation methods. It removes all the usual hardware barriers and lets us focus on teaching state-of-the-art approaches. The support team was excellent too, responding quickly even outside regular office hours. It's exactly the kind of infrastructure we need for effective training courses.

//

Dr. Benedikt Best, @EMBL Heidelberg

There are always course participants who do not download and set up the necessary software in advance, and catching them up consumes valuable teaching time. BAND is a game changer. Having the machines ready and set up has allowed us to get straight to teaching, and provides a more uniform experience for all participants. Knowing the computer environment ahead of time also makes it possible to prepare a much more specific and streamlined course programme.

Training for Standardised service delivery

Training for service providers in 2025 emphasised critical areas such as IT Service Management, aligned with the FitSM certification framework, and Information Security. The EGI Federation organised a total of 7 IT Service Management training sessions, engaging 23 service providers from across its network. 51 participants, out of 53, successfully completed the certification programme and received official credentials recognised by the APMG certification authority,

demonstrating their enhanced competencies.

By equipping service providers with standardised best practices and certified expertise, EGI not only strengthens operational maturity across the federation but also ensures the consistent delivery of reliable, secure, and high-quality computing and data services to its research communities.

Key Numbers

7

FitSM Foundation training courses

23

service providers engaged

+50

Participants in the FitSM Foundation training courses receiving an official certification

²³APMG: Agile Project Management Group, <https://apmg-international.com/>

04

Contribution to Key Policies

EGI contributes to major European policy frameworks by enabling federated digital infrastructure for research, supporting data-driven science, and strengthening interoperability across borders and disciplines

Its activities in 2025 align with key EU priorities, including the European Research Area, Open Science, the AI Continent Action Plan, the Digital Decade, and the European Strategy for Data.

The figure on the next page presents this alignment. Policy areas are shown on the left in colour-coded categories, while EGI contributions are grouped on the right. Colour links indicate how specific activities map to and support each policy area.

04 Contribution to Key Policies

Policy Area's (PA)

PA1: ERA EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA

Aims to create a unified European research space, enhancing cross-border collaboration, shared infrastructures, and mobility of researchers to strengthen Europe's competitiveness and innovation. ESFRI Research Infrastructures are a key implementation layer of this vision, enabling large-scale, transnational scientific collaboration across disciplines.

PA2: OPEN SCIENCE

Open Science facilitates sharing and collaboration, thereby accelerating the discovery process, improving research quality, and making science more impactful. The policy facilitates the development of EOSC to make European research data interoperable, accessible and reusable.

PA3: AI CONTINENT ACTION PLAN AND AI IN SCIENCE

The plan promotes large-scale AI computing infrastructure, access to high-quality data, AI adoption in strategic sectors, development of AI skills, and support for the AI Act's implementation to ensure responsible and competitive AI development across Europe.

PA4: DIGITAL DECADE

The EU's Digital Decade 2030 sets targets and objectives for Europe's digital transformation, focusing on digital skills, secure infrastructures, digitalisation of public services, and business transformation.

PA5: EUROPEAN STRATEGY FOR DATA AND COMMON EUROPEAN DATA SPACES

Aims to enable trusted, interoperable, and secure data sharing across sectors, supporting innovation, industrial growth, and scientific collaboration.

EGI Capability Group

PA1 PA3 PA4 PA5

Federated Infrastructure & Compute Services

- Connects national e-infrastructures across 40+ countries
- Provides federated infrastructure for digital services and HPC
- Enables secure, trusted access to compute, data, and digital twin frameworks
- Supports cross-border collaboration and interoperability

PA2 PA3 PA5

Open Science & Data Sharing

- Create open software platforms for large-scale data federation and processing
- Enable co-located data hosting and processing to accelerate research
- Facilitate AI-ready FAIR data for reuse
- Participate in EOSC governance and federating capabilities
- Contribute to open source software for research infrastructures

PA2 PA3 PA4 PA5

Identity, Access & Security

- Provides horizontal services like AAI, notebooks, compute-storage
- Implements federated access and interoperability models
- Supports co-development of data federation and cloud integration
- Ensures secure management of data and digital workflows

PA1 PA2 PA3

Co-Design, R&D & Research Community Support

- Supports research and innovation through co-design and co-development with communities
- Support AI adoption by research communities through co-design and user support
- Supports digital skills development initiatives

PA2 PA3 PA5

Governance, Strategy & Sustainability

- Contribute to governance, trust, and sustainability frameworks
- Participate in sectoral data spaces and link with EOSC for research data

Featured Highlights

Open Science

EGI contributes to Open Science by providing open, federated digital infrastructures that enable seamless cross-border and cross-institution access to computing, data, and digital services for research communities. Through its federation of national and institutional infrastructures, EGI ensures that scientific resources are shared and accessible beyond organisational and geographical boundaries, supporting a truly collaborative research environment. In particular, EGI enables the development and operation of open Virtual Research Environments (VREs) driven by communities of practice, allowing scientists to access tailored, scalable, and interoperable tools for data-intensive research. These environments are made widely available to researchers through the combined capacities of the national infrastructures participating in the EGI Federation, ensuring that advanced digital capabilities can be accessed in an open, inclusive, and equitable manner. EGI also participates in the EOSC task forces, projects and working groups and by contributing federating capabilities to the EOSC EU Node. In 2025 the foundations of the EGI Node application were established, resulting in a successful application in 2026.

AI in Science

EGI contributes to Europe's AI-in-Science ecosystem through the SCIANCE project, supporting the development of the Resource for AI Science in Europe (RAISE) and a community-driven approach to AI-enabled research. Within SCIANCE, EGI supports the definition of research and innovation priorities, leads the development of a roadmap for required infrastructure upgrades, contributes to the design of the RAISE Secretariat governance model, and develops the RAISE Digital Hub and Forum to enable structured engagement with scientific communities and inform the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). Through this work, EGI helps connect Research Infrastructures, AI experts and e-infrastructure providers to ensure effective integration of AI into scientific workflows across Europe.

In parallel, EGI contributes to advancing sovereign AI capabilities in Europe and supports early-stage activities towards the establishment of an EOSC AI/ML Competence Centre. Building on the FLUID-AI project, EGI contributes to the concept of Data and Models Liquidity, extending FAIR principles toward AI-ready data and models that are structured, semantically enriched and

interoperable across EOSC. FLUID-AI addresses key gaps in EOSC by introducing a coordinated Competence Centre concept for skills and support, enabling unified data/model integration for cross-platform reuse, and providing accessible AI platforms that reduce technical barriers for researchers. These activities represent an initial step towards a federated EOSC AI capability supporting trustworthy and sovereign AI services for European research.

This direction is further reinforced through RI-SCALE, where EGI coordinates development of Data Exploitation Platforms that enable scalable AI workflows over large-scale Research Infrastructure datasets. RI-SCALE brings together leading RIs, e-infrastructures and Data Spaces to prototype DEP technology, integrate AI frameworks and models, and validate interoperability with EOSC and related ecosystems.

EGI also provides a portfolio of AI services that lower the barrier to adoption of AI technologies, supporting researchers and communities in accessing scalable, reusable AI tools and expertise. These services help democratise access to AI solutions and skills across the EOSC and Research

Infrastructure landscape, complementing EGI's role in competence centre and platform development activities.

As part of its effort to expand the EGI's AI service portfolio, EGI initiated the development of FedLLM, a new federated service for deploying and operating Large Language Models for inference. FedLLM provides secure access to LLM capabilities, enabling researchers to integrate text generation, analysis, retrieval-augmented generation, and domain-specific assistants into scientific applications and workflows. The service builds on EGI's federated infrastructure model, allowing multiple providers to contribute inference capacity through a common access layer.

Complementing these efforts, in 2025, EGI concluded its coordination of iImagine project, which delivered an AI-powered platform for image analysis in aquatic ecosystems, demonstrating how domain-specific AI services can support open science and real-time environmental monitoring across marine and freshwater research communities.

EGI's Plans and Vision for the Future

In November 2025, the EGI Council approved the EGI Federation Strategy 2026–2030, setting the direction for the next five years. Building on two decades of federating computing resources across Europe, the strategy charts EGI's evolution from a computing federation into Europe's AI-ready compute-data continuum for research and innovation.

The strategy responds to five trends reshaping the research infrastructure landscape. Open science increasingly depends on systems that maintain trust and resilience across jurisdictions, as geopolitical pressures test international collaboration. Artificial intelligence has moved from specialised tool to standard expectation in research, a shift recognised by the European Commission's RAISE initiative. Demand for cross-domain infrastructure is growing, as more scientific fields require horizontal computing and data services simultaneously. Digital sovereignty is becoming an operational requirement, reinforced by the EU's 2025 Strategy on Research and Technology Infrastructures. And workforce capacity remains a bottleneck, with professionals who combine infrastructure expertise and research domain knowledge in short supply.

By 2030, EGI aims to be Europe's essential federated, AI-ready compute-data continuum for research communities: a trusted, sovereign infrastructure where researchers can access the computing power, data resources and expertise they need across borders and disciplines, and where innovation and investment compound for pan-European impact.

To realise this vision, the strategy builds on three interconnected value streams. Powering the Federation provides the shared platforms, policies and governance that hold a multi-country infrastructure together. Enabling Scientific Computing gives research communities access to AI-ready computing, data and support services. Enabling Sustained Innovation coordinates collaborative research and innovation across

the entire federation, so that results persist well beyond individual project lifecycles.

These value streams are advanced through three strategic pillars. Sovereign Compute-Data Federation focuses on integrating a European compute-data ecosystem and building AI-ready research infrastructure. Incentivised Cross-Border Access addresses the policy and funding barriers that limit resource sharing across borders. A Resilient Innovation Ecosystem positions EGI as a collaborative R&I actor whose community-led innovations endure.

With this strategy, EGI enters its next chapter with a clear mandate and a renewed sense of purpose: ensuring that European research and innovation have the trusted, sovereign, AI-ready digital foundation they need to thrive.

Finances

Income

Items	Actual 2025 (€)
Grants Income	5,250,668
Commercial Contracts income	1,899,259
Council fees	1,361,458
Other Income (paid service delivery)	218,846
TOTAL INCOME	8,730,231

Expenditure

Items	Actual 2024 (€)
Grants Costs	4,236,985
Commercial Contracts costs	1,557,130
Core service cost	741,747
Other cost (paid service delivery)	195,277
Other personnel costs	1,314,905
Office & Other Costs	604,905
ICT	104,828
Facilities	117,797
Non project Travel	30,893
Professional Costs	240,403
Communications costs	35,060
VAT	74,768
Interest expense / (income)	(37,470)
TOTAL	8,613,479

Expenses 2025

€ 8,613,479

Income 2025

€ 8,730,231

Equity 2025

€ 116,752

Our Team

The EGI Foundation is the coordinating body of the EGI Federation. It was established in 2010 with a headquarters in Amsterdam, Netherlands. The foundation staff is distributed across many countries and it ensures that the internal capabilities sustaining the federation are delivered professionally.

Our team is distributed in the following countries:

It comprises individuals from **22 different nationalities**, fostering a rich tapestry of diverse perspectives and cultural backgrounds.

Glossary

The entire glossary can be found at go.egi.eu/glossary

- **EGI:** Abbreviation of EGI Federation. Note: if EGI is mentioned, this only refers to the EGI Federation.
- **EGI Federation:** EGI Foundation, EGI Foundation Participants and Associated Participants, their linked organisations (e.g. service and resource providers) represented within EGI Foundation that contribute to the objectives of the foundation.
- **EGI Federation Core:** The EGI Federation Core is a suite of services that collectively form the backbone of the EGI infrastructure. These services are divided into two main categories: Services for Federation and Service for Research
- **EGI Foundation:** The legal entity whose objective is to coordinate and develop, in collaboration with its Participants, the EGI infrastructure that provides long-term distributed compute and storage resources for performing research and innovation activities.
- **EGI Community:** The EGI Federation plus the served research communities, the technology providers or any other organisation linked via an agreement with the EGI Foundation and contributing to the mission of the EGI Federation.
- **EOSC:** Initiative to offer researchers a virtual environment with open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis and re-use of research data, across borders and scientific disciplines.
- **EOSC Federation:** The EOSC Federation is the operational model that brings together national, regional, and thematic research infrastructures, service providers, and stakeholders to collaboratively build and operate the European Open Science Cloud.
- **HPC:** Abbreviation of High-Performance Computing. A computing paradigm that focuses on the efficient execution of compute-intensive, tightly-coupled tasks.
- **HTC:** Abbreviation of High-Throughput Compute. A computing paradigm that focuses on the efficient execution of a large number of loosely-coupled tasks.
- **NGI:** The national federation of shared computing, storage and data resources that delivers sustainable, integrated and secure distributed computing services to the national research communities and their international collaborators. The federation is coordinated by a National Coordinating Body providing a single point of contact at the national level and has official membership in the EGI Council through an NGI legal representative. Note: the name comes from "National Grid Infrastructure", which is now deprecated.
- **Virtual Organisations:** A group of people (e.g. scientists, researchers) with shared interests and requirements, who need to work collaboratively and/or share resources (e.g. data, software, expertise, CPU, storage space) regardless of geographical location.

EGI Coordinated Projects

ENVRI-Hub NEXT

ENVRI-Hub NEXT consolidates and advances the robust conceptual and technical structure established by the ENVRI-Hub

EOSC Beyond

Advancing innovation and collaboration for research

EOSC Data Commons

Building a Collaborative Future for Research Data

SPECTRUM

SPECTRUM brings together leading European science organisations and e-Infrastructure providers to formulate a Strategic Research, Innovation and Deployment Agenda (SRIDA)

RI-SCALE

RI-SCALE empowers Research Infrastructures by providing scalable computational platforms for AI-driven data analysis, improving data

2025 marked the successful conclusion of two flagship initiatives, iMagine and InterTwin. The impact reports for both projects can be accessed via the links and QR codes provided below.

IMAGINE KEY RESULTS

1. A Europe-wide AI platform for aquatic science

iMagine delivered a federated, cloud-based AI Platform for image analysis in aquatic environments, enabling researchers to develop, train, and deploy AI models at scale without needing their own high-performance infrastructure. This created a reusable, open-access foundation for AI in marine and freshwater science across Europe.

imagine-ai.eu/results-resources/imagine-impact-report

2. A large portfolio of operational AI services with real scientific impact

The project produced 18 AI models and multiple mature services (7+) supporting real-world applications such as marine litter detection, plankton identification, coral reef monitoring, fish otolith analysis, and citizen science validation. These services are already improving environmental monitoring, biodiversity assessment, and coastal risk understanding.

3. Transformation of research practice through open, collaborative AI ecosystems

iMagine significantly changed how aquatic science is conducted by shifting from manual, fragmented workflows to AI-driven, automated, and reproducible pipelines, supported by open datasets (2M+ labelled images), training, and a Competence Centre model. It also strengthened cross-disciplinary collaboration across RIs, SMEs, and European infrastructures, embedding AI more deeply into open science practice.

INTERTWIN KEY RESULTS

1. A foundational Digital Twin Engine for Europe

interTwin delivered a prototype Digital Twin Engine (DTE), an open-source platform designed to simplify the development, deployment, and operation of scientific Digital Twins. Built on open standards, APIs, and interoperable components, it provides a modular architecture (infrastructure, core, and thematic layers) enabling scalable Digital Twin applications across domains such as environmental science and physics.

intertwin.eu/article/intertwin-has-ended-whats-next

2. Integration of AI, HPC and cloud into a federated workflow ecosystem

A key achievement is the creation of a federated compute and AI ecosystem combining HTC, and cloud resources with HPC systems (e.g., EuroHPC VEGA, Jülich, PSNC) and e-infrastructures. Toolkits such as itwinai (AI workflow lifecycle management) and SQAaaS (quality and CI/CD for data, models, and software) enabled reproducible, scalable, and AI/DT workflows across distributed infrastructures.

3. Strong interoperability and real-world adoption across EOSC, DestinE and open source ecosystems

interTwin significantly advanced interoperability for Digital Twins and AI workflows, integrating with EOSC EU Node, Destination Earth, and EGI infrastructure. Components such as OSCAR, openEO, and interLink have been deployed in operational environments, reused by industry and SMEs, and even joined the CNCF Sandbox. The project also laid the foundation for continued exploitation in follow-up initiatives (e.g., RI-SCALE) and strengthened Europe's open Digital Twin and AI ecosystem.

EGI Community Participated Projects

See all projects
egi.eu/projects

Name	Start Date	End Date
ACCESS2ACCESS	01 May 2026	31 Dec 2027
ANERIS	01 Jan 2023	31 Dec 2026
Blue-Cloud 2026	01 Jan 2023	30 Jun 2026
CDIF4EOSC	01 Jun 2026	31 May 2029
DS4EU	01 Oct 2022	30 Sep 2026
DSSC2	01 May 2026	30 Apr 2029
ECHOES	01 Jun 2024	31 May 2029
EOSC Beyond	01 Apr 2024	31 Mar 2027
EOSC Data Commons	01 Apr 2025	01 Apr 2028
ENVRI-Hub NEXT	01 Feb 2024	31 Jan 2027
EOSC Gravity	01 Jun 2025	31 Dec 2027
EOSC United	01 Sep 2025	31 Aug 2028
EUCAIM	01 Jan 2023	31 Dec 2026
EUreka3D-XR	01 Feb 2025	31 Jul 2026
GreenDIGIT	01 Mar 2024	28 Feb 2027
IRISCC	01 Apr 2024	01 Oct 2028
PHENET	01 Jan 2023	31 Dec 2027
RI-SCALE	01 Mar 2025	29 Feb 2028
SAGE	01 Mar 2025	29 Feb 2028
SCIANCE	01 Dec 2025	31 May 2028
SoBigData IP	01 Jun 2026	31 May 2029
SPECTRUM	01 Jan 2024	30 Jun 2026
UNCAN-Connect	01 Sep 2025	31 Aug 2030

Key Publications

EGI Annual report 2024

The annual report offers a comprehensive overview of the remarkable achievements stemming from our collaborative endeavors in 2024. Uncover the notable milestones, projects, and initiatives that shaped the year.

egi.eu/publication/annual-report-2024

EGI Federation Strategy

This summary provides an overview of the strategic direction that allows for greater consistency of communications actions over time, which will ultimately help EGI to achieve its vision and fulfil its goals.

egi.eu/publication/egi-federation-strategy-2030

EGI Service Catalogue

Discover the power of our large-scale computing and data analysis solutions.

egi.eu/publication/egi-service-catalogue

EGI Brochure

Supporting data-intensive research with advanced computing services.

egi.eu/publication/2025-egi-brochure

EGI Support for Research Infrastructures

Solve your Digital Challenges with our Advanced Computing Solutions (2022)

egi.eu/publication/egi-for-research-infrastructures

You can find all our publications at: egi.eu/publications

Acknowledgements

EGI extends its sincere thanks to everyone who contributed to this annual report and even more importantly, to the continued advancement of the EGI Federation.

We offer special appreciation to the EGI Foundation for its coordination and leadership, and to all Federation members whose dedication remains the foundation of EGI's success.

We are also deeply grateful to the European Commission for its ongoing trust and essential funding, which enables EGI to support research, drive innovation, and advance the frontiers of open science and digital collaboration.

Contact us

Science Park 140
1098 XG Amsterdam
Netherlands

Phone:
+31 (0)20 89 32 007

Email:
contact@egi.eu

 [egieinfra.bsky.social](https://twitter.com/egieinfra.bsky.social)

 [EGI Foundation](#)

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www.egi.eu